

Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape)

2024 Annual Report (Year 4)

PI's: Adam M. Wilson & Erin Hestir; South African PI: Jasper Slingsby;
Science Team Manager: Anabelle Cardoso; Applications Coordinator: Cherié Forbes
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Summary

BioSCape, or the Biodiversity Survey of the Cape, is NASA's first biodiversity-focused airborne and field campaign. BioSCape aims to better understand the structure, function, and composition of ecosystems, and to learn about how and why they are changing in time and space. The BioSCape science team comprises 19 individually funded PI-led research projects. The campaign itself took place in South Africa in late 2023, with some data collection as well as research and analysis ongoing.

BioSCape was an exceptionally complicated mission: its Concept of Operations was unusually complex, the campaign took place in a foreign developing country, and, by design, half of the science team were affiliated with non-US institutions. Within these challenges lie opportunities: to broaden the scope of what can be accomplished in an airborne field campaign, to demonstrate the multiple benefits of international missions and diverse science teams, and to develop best practices for avoiding parachute science when working outside the US, and maximize the impact of a NASA campaign.

BioSCape has taken advantage of these opportunities and boasts significant successes to date, including:

- Executing a complex airborne and field campaign and successfully acquiring an unprecedented data set that brings us closer to measuring biodiversity from space.
- Making progress in best practices for preventing parachute science through co-developing research with end-users in mind and demonstrating a commitment to Open Science, capacity building, and outreach.
- Running an inclusive international campaign and cultivating an ethical and high-trust team dynamic.
- Garnering support and participation from multiple local, regional, and national agencies and institutions in South Africa.

BioSCape also learned many lessons which will help inform future NASA Earth Science endeavors.

In the coming year, BioSCape plans to continue its positive track record by:

- Synthesizing and communicating team science to maximize impact.
- Championing Open Science through capacity building and data equity.
- Continuing to support the application of BioSCape data in conservation.

This report was open to comment from the BioSCape Science Team, and all community feedback was incorporated before submission to NASA HQ. An accompanying document, the "BioSCape Earth Science Applications Report," details the progress towards applications of the BioSCape Project.

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Executing a successful airborne and field campaign

The campaign had an exceptionally complex Concept of Operations. BioSCape was composed of 19 PI-led science teams each with different research objectives (responsive to and broadly aligned with the BioSCape science objectives), geographically dispersed regions of interest, and often non-overlapping solar geometry / time of day requirements. Airborne data during the campaign needed to be acquired by four NASA instruments (and associated instrument teams from two NASA centers), each with different sensor geometries and flight altitude preferences. These sensors were integrated onto two NASA aircraft (from an additional two NASA centers) that then had to achieve near-simultaneous measurement of the same ground target under conditions that met the requirements of the science team. Despite the challenges, *BioSCape successfully executed a complex airborne and field campaign, acquiring an unprecedented data set that brings us closer to measuring biodiversity from space.*

BioSCape acquired airborne data over all top priority and most high and medium priority areas

- Contemporaneous measurements from AVIRIS-NG, PRISM, HyTES, and LVIS were captured across ~45,000km² in October and November 2023 (**Figure 1**).
- The GV (HyTES + LVIS) flew 16 science flights while the GIII (AVIRIS-NG + PRISM) flew 22 science flights (including two double sorties).
- This is the first time that these four instruments have all been flown together. Such a spectrally extensive dataset is unprecedented in airborne science and, when coupled with LiDAR data, has immense potential to increase its impact on the field of remote sensing of biodiversity, and remote sensing for Earth Science more broadly.
- Additionally, BioSCape partnered with the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) to fly their airborne remote-sensing platform which collected discrete return LiDAR & high resolution RGB imagery over six key estuaries in the region.
- During the campaign, EMIT captured 240 scenes over the BioSCape study region, ECOSTRESS captured 101, Sentinel-2 captured 1,051, Landsat captured 168, and GEDI has historical data across the area and has restarted acquisitions since April 2024. As such, BioSCape's airborne data have immense potential to increase the impact of NASA's current and upcoming satellite missions (including EMIT, ECOSTRESS, GEDI, PACE, and SBG).
 - PACE launched shortly after BioSCape's airborne campaign, and the "first light" image featured in their press release was of the BioSCape study region.

Figure 1: Airborne data coverage across South-Western South Africa and early airborne data products from the BioScape campaign. A) LVIS data coverage and preliminary data products (elevation, vegetation height, and structural complexity); B) AVIRIS-NG (and PRISM) data coverage as well as results of a Principal Components Analysis that can help identify vegetation communities; and C) HyTES data coverage as well as preliminary false colour images of selected bands over an important coastal water body.

BioSCape's airborne data are accompanied by an immense amount of biodiversity field data (Figure 2)

- Vegetation communities:
 - Percentage cover of dominant species in ~600 plots across environmental gradients.
 - Field spectroscopy data and plant functional traits on dominant plant species.
 - Species rarefaction curves and canopy height measurements in ~200 plots.
 - Quantifying Essential Biodiversity Variables in estuaries.
 - Biodiversity and ecosystem function measurements in plots invaded by alien plants.
 - Species surveys and field spectroscopy measurements on kelp forests.
 - Terrestrial lidar scans across neighboring vegetation stands of different post-fire age, representing a post-fire vegetation recovery sequence.
- Freshwater and marine measurements:
 - Phytoplankton and zooplankton functional type across environmental and anthropogenic gradients.
 - Colored dissolved organic matter measurements in marine environments.
 - Above and in water radiometric measurements.
 - Radiometric buoy logging continuously throughout the campaign (until January 2024, enabling sustained cal/val for local end-users).
- Animal observations:
 - “Soundscapes” from autonomous recorders across environmental gradients, especially focused on birds and frogs, but also useful for other fauna such as Orthoptera.
 - Point counts of birds and frogs.
 - Macroinvertebrate DNA sampling in rivers.
- Environmental DNA and plant DNA:
 - Environmental DNA collected across watersheds and seasons.
 - Multi-locus metabarcoding of DNA sequences across the tree of life, including major plant lineages.
 - Herbarium vouchers of dominant plant species, including many Proteaceae.

Figure 2: The BioSCape science team collecting biodiversity field data across terrestrial and marine ecosystems.

The BioSCape Leadership Team is producing research products and disseminating early campaign results

- BioSCape has produced several research papers that summarize work to date and synthesize the expected contributions of BioSCape to different aspects of remote sensing of biodiversity:
 - Cardoso, Hestir, Slingsby, Forbes, Moncrieff, Turner, Skowno, Nesslage, Brodrick, Gaddis, Wilson; in review; *The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape): Towards Inclusive International Biodiversity Science*. [[preprint](#)]
 - Cardoso, Hestir, Slingsby, Forbes, Moncrieff, Turner, Skowno, Nesslage, Brodrick, Gaddis, Wilson; in review; *The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape): Integrating Remote Sensing with Biodiversity Science*. [[preprint](#)]
 - Cardoso, Hestir, Slingsby, Nesslage, Forbes, Wilson; 2023; IGARSS - IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium in Athens, Greece; *BioSCape: Combining Airborne Hyperspectral and Laser Altimeter with Field Data to Advance Remote Sensing of Biodiversity*. [[link](#)]
- BioSCape has communicated early campaign results and expected contributions, and raised awareness of NASA Earth Data, at several events in South Africa. Many of these were to government agencies and decision makers.
 - Wilson, Cardoso, Slingsby, Hestir; 2024; Invited Seminar to the Geoinformation Information Society of South Africa (GISSA) Western Cape General Meeting; *Early Data From BioSCape: NASA's First Biodiversity-Focused Airborne Campaign*.
 - Slingsby, Wilson, Hestir, Cardoso, Forbes; 2024; Invited Seminar at the CapeNature Conservation Review; *Early results from BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
 - Slingsby, Wilson, Hestir, Cardoso, Forbes; 2024; Invited Seminar to the CapeNature Board and Chief Executive Officer; *Early results from BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
 - Slingsby, Wilson, Hestir, Cardoso, Forbes; 2024; Invited Seminar to the Botanical Society of South Africa; *BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
 - Slingsby, Wilson, Hestir, Cardoso, Forbes; 2024; Invited Seminar to CapeNature - Landscape West; *Early results from BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
 - Wilson, Slingsby, Hestir, Cardoso, Forbes; 2024; Invited Seminar to the Centre for Statistics in Ecology, the Environment and Conservation at the University of Cape Town; *Data from BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
 - Cardoso, Wilson, Slingsby, Hestir, Forbes; 2024; Invited Seminar to The Nature Conservancy; *Early results from BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
 - Cardoso, Wilson, Slingsby, Hestir, Forbes; 2024; Invited Seminar to The South African Environmental Observation Network; *Early results from BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
 - Slingsby, Wilson, Hestir, Cardoso, Forbes; 2023; Invited Seminar at the Cape Floristic Region Partnership Annual General Meeting; *BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
 - Slingsby, Wilson, Hestir, Cardoso, Forbes; 2023; Invited Seminar to CapeNature - Landscape Central; *Early results from BioSCape: The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape*.
- Similarly, BioSCape has communicated early campaign results and expected contributions at various events in the USA and abroad, including international conferences and NASA-run workshops.

- Wilson, Slingsby, Cardoso, Forbes, Hestir; 2024; World Biodiversity Forum in Davos, Switzerland; *BioSCape: Early Results From The Biodiversity Survey Of The Cape*.
- Cardoso, Hestir, Wilson, Slingsby, Forbes, Brodrick; 2024; SBG Technical Interchange Meeting in Washington, DC; *NASA's first biodiversity-focused airborne campaign: An unprecedented suite of instruments collecting data across terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems in South Africa*.
- Hestir, Cardoso, Slingsby, Forbes, Wilson; 2024; NASA BDEC Team Meeting in Washington, DC; *BioSCape: Updates from the campaign*.
- Brodrick, Cardoso, Wilson, Hestir, Slingsby, Forbes; 2024; EARSeL Workshop on Imaging Spectroscopy in Valencia, Spain; *Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape): A NASA campaign to understand Earth's biodiversity through the lens of spectroscopy*.
- Cardoso, Wilson, Slingsby, Forbes, Moncrieff, Cawse-Nicholson, Brodrick, Hestir; 2023; AGU Annual Meeting in San Francisco, CA; *BioSCape: Early results from NASA's first biodiversity-focussed field campaign in South Africa*.
- Hestir, Wilson, Cardoso, Slingsby, Forbes; 2023; Optica Sensing Congress in Munich, Germany; *The NASA Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape)*.
- Biggs, Forbes, Wilson, Slingsby, Hestir, Cardoso, Tekeei, Wigbels, Leidner, Chen; 2023; AGU Annual Meeting in San Francisco, CA; *Biodiversity Champions: Uniting with South African Students During the BioSCape Campaign*.

BioSCape is relevant to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

South Africa is a signatory of the Convention of Biological Diversity and mandated to report on progress towards the [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#) (“The Biodiversity Plan”). This reporting is done at the national level thus it’s unlikely that BioSCape products will feed directly into the headline indicators. However, BioSCape paves the way for the use of satellite remote sensing and imaging spectroscopy for aiding and tracking progress towards the GBF Goals and Targets in future. Its relevance to several of the targets are briefly outlined below and detailed further throughout this report.

|
BioSCape
Impact |
|---|--|
| <u>Goal A:</u>
Protect and Restore | BioSCape will contribute towards mapping ecosystem extent and integrity/condition, for example, mapping different functional communities and alien plant invasions or selected taxa. BioSCape will also contribute to population, distribution and data on threats that underpin species and ecosystem threat assessments. |
| <u>Goal D:</u>
Invest and Collaborate | Through significant investment by the United States and South African governments, BioSCape is building technical capacity in both countries. The project is an example of positive international cooperation working towards equitably Open Data practices. |
| <u>Target 1</u>
Plan and Manage all Areas To Reduce Biodiversity Loss | Develop and test new technologies and methods to produce data products relevant to biodiversity-inclusive spatial planning and effective management processes. |

<p><u>Target 2</u> Restore 30% of all Degraded Ecosystems</p>	<p>By helping to identify degraded ecosystems and indicators of recovery, BioSCape can inform restoration planning and monitoring efforts.</p>
<p><u>Target 3</u> Conserve 30% of Land, Waters and Seas</p>	<p>By helping identify biodiversity hotspots and key novel habitats and by assessing the threats to and condition of ecosystems, BioSCape will help inform conservation planning and management. Improved mapping of ecosystem extent contributes to improved planning and reporting.</p>
<p><u>Target 4</u> Halt Species Extinction, Protect Genetic Diversity, and Manage Human-Wildlife Conflicts</p>	<p>BioSCape is contributing towards conservation of threatened species by helping to build a better understanding of distribution and abundance trends, for example through audio monitoring of birds and a better understanding of the relationship between species and ecosystems.</p>
<p><u>Target 6</u> Reduce the Introduction of Invasive Alien Species by 50% and Minimize Their Impact</p>	<p>BioSCape is helping create maps of invasive alien species and increasing our understanding of how they affect ecosystem function. This can assist efforts to eliminate, minimize, reduce and mitigate their impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services.</p>
<p><u>Target 7</u> Reduce Pollution to Levels That Are Not Harmful to Biodiversity</p>	<p>BioSCape is helping develop better Harmful Algal Bloom detection algorithms that will benefit monitoring of coastal and inland water eutrophication, aiding pollution management and aquaculture, mariculture, and fisheries industries.</p>
<p><u>Target 11</u> Restore, Maintain and Enhance Nature's Contributions to People</p>	<p>BioSCape will contribute towards better management of terrestrial invasive alien species. This is an essential part of maintaining and improving freshwater supply, reducing fire hazards, and maintaining biodiversity and the aesthetic of landscapes.</p>
<p><u>Target 14</u> Integrate Biodiversity in decision making at Every Level</p>	<p>BioSCape's research is relevant to decision-makers in South Africa, and we hope to bring the BioSCape data products to these decision-makers as they are produced.</p>
<p><u>Target 20</u> Strengthen Capacity-Building, Technology Transfer, and Scientific and Technical Cooperation for Biodiversity</p>	<p>BioSCape is engaged in capacity-building and scientific cooperation in a developing country and strongly focuses on co-developing joint scientific research, skills, and technology transfer.</p>
<p><u>Target 21</u> Ensure That Knowledge Is Available and Accessible To Guide Biodiversity Action</p>	<p>BioSCape is making a concerted effort to ensure that all campaign data follows Open Science principles and is equitable - for example, the BioSCape Cloud Environment reduces barriers to access for South African users.</p>

BioSCape is scientifically valuable

- The BioSCape science team was surveyed after the field campaign to gather feedback about the campaign's scientific value, perceptions of international collaboration, and experiences of campaign execution.
- 56 people responded to the survey, and 100% agreed that BioSCape is scientifically valuable and will advance the state of knowledge (**Figure 3**).

- When asked what people loved about BioSCape (free text response), 46% of respondents mentioned the scientific value of the campaign and the inclusion of applications. Some quotes on this topic included:
 - "BioSCape makes me feel like I am applying my research in real world application and conservation efforts for the better future."
 - "Bringing together scientists with different expertise and methods towards a broad, unifying goal."
 - "It probably was the first time as a grad student that I felt like a scientist that was doing something really important in the world."
 - "Being exposed to such a cross section of work using hyperspectral imaging was mind blowing."
 - "I loved the networking component of BioSCape, especially the Applications workshop."
- Notably, 7 respondents mentioned the importance of the Applications Workshop, indicating that "it was an essential BioSCape activity".

Figure 3: Survey responses on the perception of BioSCape's scientific value by the science team (N=56).

BioSCape was well executed with an excellent team dynamic

- 56 people responded to the survey, and 100% agreed that the BioSCape campaign was well executed (**Figure 4**).
- When asked what people loved about BioSCape (free text response), 33% of respondents mentioned the organization, efficiency, and inclusivity of the BioSCape leadership team. Some quotes on this topic included:
 - "The effort made by the leadership team to be inclusive for all team members."
 - "Extremely well organised despite complexity of the programme."
 - "Well organised and an example of how multi-disciplinary and multi-national projects should be run."

- “The leadership team was exceptional at co-ordination and communication, and were very responsive to the particular needs of our field team.”
- “I loved the leadership team, because they thought and planned about 'every' aspect of the campaign.”

Figure 4: Survey responses on the perception of BioSCape's campaign execution by the science team (N=56).

BioSCape's "Lessons Learned" for improving the execution of future airborne and field campaigns:

- BioSCape did not scope using commercial aircraft. This resulted in a lack of redundancy for the US government shutdown, possibly more costly flight operations, difficulty obtaining flight clearances for government aircraft, and unpredictable intra-agency relationships that threatened the entire mission.
- We did plan for test/integration flights in the US for both aircraft before the campaign, however we did not schedule these early enough. Both aircraft had very full schedules, and this resulted in the GV only doing test flights/integration immediately prior to the campaign. Unfortunately, this resulted in instrument calibration issues with HyTES that did not get resolved in the US, and thus continued in the first weeks of the campaign. This affected ConOps for all 4 instruments and data quality for HyTES throughout the campaign.
- While regions of interest were identified prior to the campaign, we did not have flight lines/coordinates generated in advance of the campaign that accounted for instrument geometry for each aircraft, and needed to create them on the fly. This made flight operations less smooth and more stressful than was optimal. We note that some on-the-fly planning is feasible and indeed necessary, but a pre-loaded bank of flight lines would have been advisable. Further, the specifications and requirements for each

instrument, and the format required for flightlines for each aircraft were different, and dictated in part by the hardware of the aircraft. Advance planning with instrument and aircraft teams, including pilots or pilot representatives for each aircraft, would further mitigate just-in-time planning and improve communication between science and flight operations.

- We were not able to resolve the proper sample export procedures to comply with the [Nagoya Protocol for Access and Benefit Sharing](#) (Nagoya Protocol) before the campaign. The US is not a signatory to the Nagoya Protocol and thus compliance is not required, but we sought to comply voluntarily out of respect for the protocol. While we eventually resolved the path to export permits, the process was far slower and more difficult than we anticipated. We recommend that other campaigns prioritize getting this sorted out as soon as possible, well in advance of samples being collected, and ideally before research permit applications are made. Furthermore, adherence to Nagoya is highly dependent on local policies and regulations, and thus local/regional expertise and local contacts are recommended.

Reducing parachute science

By design, BioSCape has a diverse and international Science Team, with over 150 members, 19 independent PI-led research projects, and approximately equal participation from South African- and US- affiliated researchers. Due to US Federal funding restrictions on direct funding of non-US affiliated team members, despite our best efforts there were funding inequities between US and SA affiliated science team members. Additionally, the science team was diverse in scientific discipline, proximity to end-users, field experience, local knowledge, technical capacity, and culture. Consequently, the project was vulnerable to parachute science. Being aware of this risk, *BioSCape has made progress towards preventing parachute science through co-developing research with end-users in mind and demonstrating a commitment to Open Science, capacity building, and outreach.*

BioSCape co-designed its research with South African end-users in mind

- As soon as BioSCape was funded, in the first half of 2021, the leadership team hosted an online Networking Workshop. This introductory workshop covered developments within the initial phases of BioSCape. It included presentations by the BioSCape PIs, NASA, NSF, the University of Cape Town, SANBI, SAEON, South African National Parks (SANParks), and CapeNature.
- In 2022, BioSCape also had an online Parachute Science Workshop. This workshop overviewed challenges and outlined pivotal steps in preventing parachute science with a focus on projects related to remote sensing of the environment and biodiversity.
- The team also ran a 2021 AGU Fall Meeting workshop entitled *Meaningful and equitable collaboration: How to avoid parachute science.*
- We ran an effective Science Applications Workshop in May 2023. The workshop allowed members of the science team to meet with and listen to the needs of local practitioners (data users and decision-makers from end-users and boundary agency organisations) and take these into account when planning their research.
- BioSCape repeatedly showcased South African expertise. For example, representatives of the local biodiversity and conservation agencies were invited to present at Science Team Meetings and the in-person Science Applications workshop. This ensured that local ideas, needs, and advice could be incorporated into the research projects' planning.
- The leadership team secured UNESCO funding for the SA PI (Slingsby) to develop capacity and support SA members of the Science Team. This funding is significantly

more flexible than US federal funding, especially for expenses such as travel and other activities of SA-affiliated team members.

- South African Co-PI Slingsby was part of the project from day one (the pre-proposal in 2015). Slingsby has a wealth of local knowledge and is connected to many biodiversity conservation spaces in South Africa. As such, his presence on the team ensured that BioSCape's scientific direction was designed to meet local needs.
- The ROSES funding call explicitly stated that proposals co-developed with SA researchers would be more likely to be funded. After the ROSES funding calls were released, we organized an online networking event to help connect interested scientists from the US and SA and encourage collaboration on proposals. This ensured that all research teams had SA team members and that the BioSCape Science Team overall was about half SA- and half US-affiliated members.
- During the development of the BioSCape scoping proposal, the PIs engaged with South African research institutions, including the SA National Research Foundation (NRF) (the equivalent of US NSF) and SA National Space Agency (SANSA) (the equivalent of US NASA). The SANSA Chief Scientist was very supportive and explicitly highlighted BioSCape in a funding call in 2021 that resulted in two SA-led projects (total 43 team members) whose research was funded through the NRF's NEOfrontiers program, thus ensuring SA scientists were funded to participate in the campaign, though not fully overcoming funding inequities. These teams and their requirements were given equal status to the NASA-funded teams during flight and field planning and operations.

BioSCape is committed to Open Science and capacity building

- BioSCape has adopted an open approach to the project from the start, and all materials are in the open domain where possible (i.e. where they don't infringe on intellectual property or other sensitive information). For example, most code and analyses used for planning are open on the BioSCape GitHub (<https://github.com/BioSCape-io>) and much other content is made available via the website (www.bioscape.io).
- BioSCape secured funding from Amazon Web Services which, in collaboration with GSFC's Science Managed Cloud Environment, have enabled us to stand up a cloud computing environment for BioSCape. Cloud computing is essential for BioSCape - the airborne and satellite datasets are very large and users in South Africa have bandwidth constraints and hardware constraints that make analyzing these datasets unfeasible. The Cloud environment is developing in-country capacity for data processing skills, empowering users to handle current and expected NASA Earth Data products from EMIT, PACE, ECOSTRESS, GEDI, and SBG.
- In addition to traditional L1 and L2 products, BioSCape will produce a co-registered mosaic of L2 data from all four instruments. This is the first time an airborne campaign has done this, and we expect it to dramatically increase the data's accessibility, especially for new users.
- Given the complexity and novelty of the BioSCape data, we are holding weekly "Office Hours" for the science team to have their data processing questions addressed.
- BioSCape leveraged NASA's commitment to secure additional funding from UNESCO, which is supporting a South African PhD student and a researcher to attend an international conference, visit a US University for an extended skills exchange, and run a capacity-building workshop.
- Worked with NASA's Applied Remote Sensing Training (ARSET) program to host a training webinar series that focussed on the BioSCape sensors and how they could be applied to biodiversity monitoring. The webinar has been viewed by 2580 people.
- With the University of Wisconsin, the University of California Merced, and the University of Cape Town, we hosted a two-day in-person field spectroscopy training workshop for

researchers and practitioners at the beginning of the airborne campaign. Twenty-two researchers and practitioners from universities, government organizations, and NGOs attended the workshop.

- In preparation for the campaign, in collaboration with the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) and the Nature Conservancy we held a multi-week capacity building workshop on accessing and using EMIT data using Python notebooks. This was held in person at the University of Cape Town and was recorded for those attending remotely.
- Worked with NASA's ORNL DAAC to present a training webinar on the NASA DAACs, what they do, how to use them to archive your data, and Open Data best practices.
- Stellenbosch University offers accredited short courses in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Earth Observation (EO). This year, 8 seats were funded by the South African-funded research projects on BioSCape.
- To improve science communication on the team, we funded 20 science team members (7 SA, 13 USA, 50% ECR) to attend a 4-day COMPASS Science Communication workshop. Workshop participants provided survey feedback and indicated that they most enjoyed engaging with the journalists, learning about their world, and receiving feedback directly from them; learning different ways to tell different stories about their work; and learning communication strategies and tools to simplify their messages.
- In collaboration with BioSCape, the South African Department of Water and Sanitation and the Centre for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) ran a 2-day in-person workshop in Cape Town designed for end users working in water resource and water quality monitoring and management. The training provided an introduction to remote sensing concepts, specifically tailored to the observation of water targets, with an overview of the current freely available satellite platforms, data, and services.

BioSCape supported several community outreach events during the campaign (Figure 6)

- We held a public lecture at the University of Cape Town attended by >150 local stakeholders and members of the public, including >20 members of local government.
- With support from the aircraft, instrument, and ESPO teams, we held a "Meet the Plane Open Day" where >50 local stakeholders could tour the NASA plane, learn about the instruments, and engage with NASA personnel.
- A school education program run by NASA's Global Learning and Observation to Benefit the Environment (GLOBE) program that reached 70 students from 10 high schools in the Western Cape (6 from under-resourced township schools).
- Two NASA SpaceApps events for local school kids (notably, one of the global winners was from a BioSCape submission),
- Presentations from various members of the Science Team at the Graduate Student Conference for the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON).
- School assembly presentation to Bay Primary School learners.

BioSCape is a good example of productive international collaboration

- 56 people responded to the survey, and 100% agreed that BioSCape's international collaboration enabled better science (**Figure 5**).
- When asked what people loved about BioSCape (free text response), 67% of respondents mentioned international collaboration and networking. Some quotes on this topic included:
 - "Collaboration with our South African colleagues was great! The warmth of the people of South Africa is unique."

- "Great partnership and collaboration between South African and US researchers, exposing students to great science and supervision."
- "The amazing support that we got from our South Africa collaborators and their determination to get things done was really wonderful."
- "Our collaboration has been phenomenal."
- "The people we met and worked with incredibly engaged, even when (especially when!) things were difficult."
- Notably, when the survey asked what people hated about BioSCape, 26% of respondents mentioned funding, making it the most common answer to this question. Two pain points were mentioned repeatedly:
 - "NASA funding levels were too low for this kind of international campaign."
 - "Navigating NASA's funding policies for non-US affiliates proved challenging... lacking funding avenues for South African researchers."

Figure 5: Survey responses on the perception of BioSCape's international collaboration by the science team (N=56).

BioSCape's "Lessons Learned" for reducing parachute science in future campaigns

- BioSCape faced challenges in identifying and obtaining adequate funding for all SA-affiliated researchers. Despite securing some non-NASA funding, it would have been beneficial to explore additional avenues for funding from both the US and SA.
 - The BioSCape team did seek funding from USAID and SERVIR; however, the campaign fell outside of their region. They also sought funding from philanthropic organizations but were unsuccessful.

- There was a large disparity in the available funding to US and SA team members that resulted in asymmetric opportunities across the team. We experienced difficulty in identifying funding sources to cover travel expenses for our SA-affiliated team members to team events. This included travel to meetings or field sites. Although SA researchers were, in most cases, able to find funding for their local travel expenses, few of the SA-affiliated team members had the financial means to travel to the US and collaborate with their team, conduct lab visits to exchange skills, or present their findings at conferences. This creates an imbalance where such opportunities are only accessible to US-affiliated team members.
 - Conversations with Earth Action Program Managers after the fact indicated that perhaps NASA was more flexible than we realized. Early engagement with the relevant program early in the process may have led to more creative solutions.
- We did not openly provide pay guidelines for field assistants and other consultants at the proposal writing stage, and therefore could not ensure that teams budgeted appropriately or that there was equity across the project.
- We failed to discourage the use of free or volunteer labor, especially by students, at the proposal writing stage. Relying on volunteers proved both risky for the project (it is hard to find people) and potentially exploitative (students are less financially stable in SA than in the US). Projects should have appropriately budgeted for the labor their data collection required.
- We did not explicitly encourage teams to familiarize themselves with their institutions' funding infrastructure for international payments and start working on contractor agreements and other necessary paperwork earlier in the process. We also did not instruct teams to be proactively transparent and communicative about what services are being provided by local consultants. This resulted in differences in expectations and delays in payment.
- Despite our best attempts, we were not able to develop a formal MOU or similar agreement early in the process with partner organizations (such as the SA Department of Science and Innovation and/or SA National Space Agency). This ended up creating friction with local institutions and obstacles for obtaining official permissions to collect data. We were able to navigate these challenges, but a more formal arrangement would have been helpful. We suggest starting this process as soon as local partners are identified and project funding is confirmed. We also suggest approaching multiple partners where appropriate, reducing reliance on individuals and personal relationships or single institutions for the success of the project, as this may be derailed by staff turnover or instability in the partner institution.
 - Local context and international relations should be considered before pursuing formal MOUs and agreements, and long lead-times are likely necessary to execute such agreements, and would require substantial overhead and appropriate institutional support. For example, BioSCape itself is not an entity, and thus unable to sign or execute an MOU with other partners. Early in the process an MOU or Letter of Agreement between NASA OIIR and SANSA was pursued, but not fully executed by the time of the campaign, despite significant efforts. In hindsight, we should have explored an MOU with SAEON, who were instrumental in providing local support in the end.
- We did not explicitly budget for capacity building activities. This is, in part, due to the nature of the funding call that supported the campaign; but alternative funding sources or funded partners that could support capacity building activities should have been identified and secured earlier in the project. Specific activities that BioSCape needed funding to support included:

- Setting up the cloud environment and the cost of buying compute credits to support running it.
- Labor costs for creating coding notebooks and other teaching materials for the BioSCape data.
- Labor costs for troubleshooting the early stages of airborne data analysis with new users, particularly on the cloud environment.
- Local travel for SA participants, venue hire, and lunch for capacity building workshops.
- We needed more support to create teaching materials for beginner to intermediate users. This would have ideally helped create more coding notebooks and supported the running of data analysis office hours. BioSCape is filling this gap with help from the ORNL DAAC, JPL, and the SMCE team at GSFC, but capacity is very limited and largely out of scope of people's expected roles (ie. based on goodwill).
- We did not communicate the logistical burden that would likely be placed on local collaborators early on. This resulted in local team members feeling like they were unfairly burdened with administrative overhead such as receiving shipments, storing equipment and samples, processing and shipping samples, and signing contracts and forms. To address this issue in future projects, we recommend that this burden be discussed and that US-affiliated team members plan to allocate extra non-field time in-country to assist with this logistical burden, which often takes longer than expected. It is also highly recommended that US-affiliated team members make time and budget appropriately to visit their local collaborating institution and meet the administrative and support staff who will be helping with project administration tasks, as this helps maintain positive relationships amid ceaseless email requests for assistance.
 - Fortunately, the applications workshop convened in May 2023 reduced what could have been substantially more friction around this topic, as it created an opportunity for teams to meet, plan, and foster goodwill outside of the workshop hours. Future projects should be more deliberate in this process.
- We did not budget for outreach events critical to local buy-in and maximizing impact, such as the public lecture, and had to use UNESCO funding for these.

Figure 6: BioSCape's outreach events during the campaign.

Running an inclusive international campaign

In the lead-up to and during BioSCape there was a looming US government shutdown and strained US-South Africa diplomatic relations due to the ongoing conflict between Russia and Ukraine. Consequently, there were a myriad of stakeholders in various government and research organizations in South Africa and at the US State Department who hoped that BioSCape would be a tool for scientific diplomacy and relationship building. The campaign was therefore an important opportunity to maintain and enhance NASA's reputation internationally and build goodwill between the US and South Africa. To take advantage of this opportunity, *BioSCape focused on running an inclusive international campaign and cultivating an ethical and high-trust team dynamic.*

BioSCape engaged with ethical collaboration best practices

- BioSCape ran a workshop (co-hosted by the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) and the University of California Santa Cruz) that introduced the “Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity” and explained how to comply with it. The workshop included putting together a document outlining the shared benefits of each team’s planned research, detailing the ways both SA and US counterparts benefitted from the research. Such a document was important for managing expectations and keeping teams focused on the benefits of international collaboration.
- Prior to the campaign, we wrote a comprehensive Code of Conduct. We included explicit authorship guidelines in the Code of Conduct, and repeatedly reminded the Science Team about these, encouraging them to have conversations with collaborators about authorship and expectations early and often.
- Over 100 science team members underwent “Ethical Participation” pre-field training. The training covered the Code of Conduct, methods for conflict resolution in the field, basic field safety in South Africa, and the country's historical, sociopolitical, and cultural context.
- During the campaign, we monitored responses on a Google form for incidents of bullying and harassment. This form allowed people to report incidents and to give feedback to the leadership team on how the campaign was being run (anonymously if desired).
 - No incidents were reported during the campaign. However, several verbal “concerns” were raised that required some leadership intervention. Most of these were centered around miscommunication and mismatched expectations between the parties. To our knowledge, all conflicts in which leadership intervened were resolved satisfactorily for both parties.
- During the campaign, various social events were organized to ensure team cohesion and foster goodwill between US and South African participants. These included a welcome barbecue featuring South African cuisine (known as a “Braai”) and an American-themed Thanksgiving dinner. There was also a WhatsApp group that coordinated social activities and shared local tourism tips.

BioSCape consciously cultivated a transparent and high-trust team dynamic

- From very early in the project, we solicited prioritized regions of interest from each PI, and PIs were able to continue updating these regions up until data were acquired. Having an approximate list of requests early allowed us to temper expectations for what may or may not be possible based on our available flight hours. Using these ROIs, we developed a prioritization algorithm that allowed us to reduce bias in flight decisions. The algorithm increased the priority of sites where multiple projects requested acquisitions

and sites that represented a high proportion of the area required by a project for its success. This prioritization was shared with the science team, so that teams could manage their expectations and feel confident that flight decisions made by the leadership team were transparent.

- We used the Visions/MMGIS platform to transparently convey flight plans to the science team and deliver Quicklook imagery in near real-time. This ensured that PIs felt that their interests were being accounted for and that the success of their project was being appropriately weighted.
- We invited the whole science team to the daily forecasting and flight planning calls. While the majority of Science Team members did not regularly attend, having the flight decision making process be open helped build trust in the team. In recognition that several teams were working in remote field conditions and may not be able to attend forecasting calls synchronously, with support from ESPO we also maintained a daily communication schedule through email and WhatsApp for all team members to be informed of progress and plans. As a result, we received very few complaints from PI's and there was no conflict on the team about when and where airborne data was being acquired. Flight planning and decision making were done transparently from the beginning, using a combination of algorithms, open discussion, and regular PI check-ins.
- We developed a Communications Strategy document in collaboration with the US Embassy and NASA Communications teams. This included preferred language and Key Messaging points, as well as a draft press release. We proactively engaged with local journalists and University press offices to publicise the campaign prior to the planes arriving in SA. During the campaign, several "conspiracy" stories gained traction in social media, but these were effectively shut down by local journalists (without our prompting or involvement) as well as other social media followers as they were already familiar with our project - some having visited the planes, photographed them inside, and interviewed members of the leadership team about our science goals.

BioSCape's "Lessons Learned" for running an inclusive campaign

- Use of the Visions/MMGIS platform was essential to project success. While implementation of this tool was timely, we could have onboarded the Science Team to the platform earlier (and reminded them more often) to ensure that everyone was utilizing the tool to its full capacity.
- We did not budget for pre-field ethical and safety training - while we found money to pay for this, it would have been beneficial to have money set aside in advance.
- We should have written and circulated the Code of Conduct earlier in the project, which may have encouraged more people to actively engage with it.
- We did not check that teams had completed their document outlining shared benefits, therefore it is possible that teams did not engage with this as deeply as would have been optimal.
- We did not budget for social and networking events, including things like a welcome event during the campaign, a public lecture, or any kind of networking meetup at a conference. All such events were crucial for building and maintaining a positive team culture but had to be funded by limited ad hoc funding sources.

Looking Forward

Delays this year

BioSCape's airborne data products were delayed - with AVIRIS-NG being released in April 2024, LVIS and PRISM released in May 2024, and HyTES still forthcoming. Consequently, we anticipate the majority of science teams to request an extension on their projects. Following

typical academic publishing timelines, we do not expect final data products and research papers from the science team until mid-2025 and beyond.

Plans for the Coming Year

BioSCape plans to maximize impact in the coming year across the following activities:

- Synthesize and communicate team science:
 - Hold a Science Team Meeting for the sharing of early results and discussion on productive ways forward.
 - Presenting BioSCape data at local and international conferences and meetings to keep stakeholders informed and encourage broader uptake of the products.
 - Producing a manuscript that details the data collected during the campaign.
 - Producing a manuscript that synthesizes BioSCape's key findings.
- Champion Open Science through capacity building and data equity:
 - Continued collaboration with ORNL DAAC and science team to ensure timely publication of BioSCape datasets.
 - Working with the Science Team to ensure timely communication and publication of research findings.
 - Expanded access to and use of cloud-based computing via the BioSCape Cloud.
 - Continued collaboration with NASA's SMCE at GSFC, Amazon Web Services, and NASA's ORNL DAAC to support capacity-building workshops and the production of training materials.
- Continue support for the application of BioSCape data in conservation:
 - Continued participation in regional networks and conferences to ensure BioSCape results and products are used to their full potential.
 - Interfacing with existing applications partners and science team members, and providing a centralized contact point and conduit between potential new applications interests and science team members.

With additional funding, BioSCape can further increase its impact through the following activities:

- Broaden scientific impact:
 - Longer term centralized support for the science team, data products, and team meetings.
 - Notably, the second most mentioned "thing people hated" about BioSCape (after funding inequities) in the feedback survey was the lack of opportunity for collaboration across projects (21% of respondents). We believe continued centralized project support would go a long way towards facilitating this.
 - Additional participation in local and international conferences to encourage broader uptake of the data products.
- Support capacity building and foster new Earth Data user communities:
 - Holding 'office hours' and creating extended "read the docs" help manuals for current and potential data users to ensure successful data uptake by troubleshooting onboarding problems with the BioSCape Cloud environment and common data analysis roadblocks.
- Support decision makers in applying BioSCape data, especially to inform biodiversity conservation.
 - Hosting a second Applications workshop to (a) close the loop with existing stakeholders and assist with training and interpretation of BioSCape data products that support decision making, (b) to showcase any additional

serendipitous data products or opportunities, and (c) create and maintain deep and sustaining collaborations with the Science Team.